

“Sleeve gastrectomy vs. Roux-en-Y gastric bypass: Nutritional deficiencies and gut-microbial changes.”

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Introduction

Bariatric surgery is a key long-term treatment for morbid obesity and related comorbidities, with Sleeve Gastrectomy (SG) and Roux-en-Y gastric bypass (RYGB) being the most common procedures. Although both are highly effective, SG is mainly restrictive, while RYGB is both restrictive and malabsorptive. These differences in mechanisms may affect long-term outcomes, especially micronutrient deficiencies and gut microbiota changes. This review aims to compare and evaluate the procedures' nutritional and metabolic consequences.

Materials and methods

Scientific literature was obtained from PubMed (2016–2026) using the keywords “micronutrient deficiencies”, “sleeve gastrectomy”, “Roux-en-Y”, and “gut microbiota”. In this narrative review, twenty-five relevant studies were selected, and reviewed.

Results

It was evident that multiple micronutrient deficiencies arose after bariatric surgery, with vitamin B12, iron, and calcium being most affected. Mechanical restriction, malabsorption, and an altered gastric environment are the main mechanisms behind these deficiencies. Although SG and RYGB both carry significant risk, RYGB shows a higher reported prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency (37–50%), iron deficiency (18–53%), and a greater association with secondary hyperparathyroidism. The higher risk in RYGB is a consequence of the anatomical and physiological alterations. Research has also shown changes in the gut microbiota after both procedures, including increased diversity and taxonomic shifts (decrease in Firmicutes and increase in Bacteroidetes and Proteobacteria). These microbial changes may influence nutrient transport and utilization, suggesting that the gut microbiota could compete with the host for nutrients. In RYGB, oral bacterial invasion and elevated Proteobacteria have been associated with increased risk of small intestinal bacterial overgrowth, which may worsen malabsorption.

Conclusion

SG and RYGB are highly effective bariatric procedures with different long-term nutritional and microbial effects. RYGB may achieve greater weight loss but is associated with higher micronutrient deficiencies and greater gut microbiome changes. Overall, the long-term success with either technique depends on proper pre-operative assessment, lifelong supplementation, and multidisciplinary monitoring.

Keywords

Bariatric Surgery, Sleeve Gastrectomy, Roux-en-Y gastric bypass, Nutritional deficiencies, Gut-microbiota.